

LOSS AND GAPS: EVALUATION OF LEARNING ACTIVITY SHEETS

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Loss and Gaps: Evaluation of Learning Activity Sheets

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the learning activity sheets (LAS) in English, which served as inputs for an action plan for the school year 2023-2024. Based on the result of the study, the English expert respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.64 with the verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree, while the teacher-respondents got an overall weighted mean of 3.72, which is also verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. There is no significant difference between the two groups of respondents' evaluations regarding the appropriateness, accuracy, usefulness, clarity, and comprehensibility on the developed learning activity sheets.

Keywords: *loss, gaps, learning, activity sheets*

Introduction

Education is an important tool which is very useful in everybody's life. It is what differentiates us from other living beings on earth. It makes man the smartest creature on earth. It empowers humans and prepares them to face life's challenges efficiently. Having mentioned these ideas, teachers then need to realize that their teaching should be very effective and efficient. They should be able to use instructional materials that cater to better teaching and learning.

Utilizing instructional material is linked to advancing knowledge and technology while consistent with national and educational objectives. Educators convey the subject, and learners acquire it through daily tasks that become routines. Learners, of course, require engaging instructional materials to gather information during the learning process; therefore, learning materials with exciting innovations are required to motivate students to learn.

In the delivery of instructions, instructional materials serve as a conduit between the teacher and the students. They may also be used to motivate students during the teaching-learning process. It is used to keep students' attention and alleviate boredom. Lesson plans are frequently based on instructional materials. Teachers will also require these tools in order to assess their pupils' knowledge. Teachers frequently evaluate pupils by assigning assignments, developing projects, and administering tests. Instructional materials are required for all of these activities. The alignment of the activity sheets with the curriculum was one of the principles that the teacher should always keep in mind when developing instructional material. The target competencies needed to be met in order to improve the learning process.

The policy under DepEd Order No. 18 series of 2020 aims to establish the guidelines that will enable the Department of Education (DepEd) to provide learning resources and implement the Basic Education - Learning Continuity Plan (BE - LCP) to ensure that learning opportunities should be safely provided to the learners, using various learning delivery methods. LAS were included in SLMs and are used to assess the learners' level of knowledge throughout the course.

The LAS measures learners' ability to understand and integrate or perform what they've learned. The sheet is crucial in encouraging children to absorb and internalize the information presented. The teacher can monitor learners who have grasped the content and those who have not yet grasped it while concentrating on the activity sheet. This sheet is one of the teaching materials used to enhance the teacher's function and is critical to the learning process's efficacy. With LAS, which is based on scientific principles, the teacher's role is reduced to that of a facilitator rather than the primary source of learning. Students are expected to identify difficulties, consider alternate solutions, and assess the settlement results while working on activity sheets. Because it was made general, the learners were only taught about the subject that the teacher had previously taught, and no problem-solving abilities were taught. The student activity sheets are important in the learning process because they feature learning activities in which all students can participate visually, audibly, or physically.

Several studies have shown that instructional materials increase the teaching and learning process while allowing teachers and students to engage as human beings in a setting where people control their surroundings for their best interests. It also demonstrated that instructional materials can achieve a wide range of complicated tasks when employed effectively in teaching-learning contexts. It also provides real-life experiences for teachers, providing them with a foundation for thinking and comprehending. It also provides a realistic foundation for conceptual thinking, reducing the number of nonsensical responses from students.

The teacher can use instructional resources to assess the learner's challenges. It makes it possible for students to understand concepts more quickly and efficiently. It also aids in the clarification of information by simplifying, highlighting, and emphasizing it. In terms of academic attainment, worksheets can be helpful in several ways. Worksheets, for example, can be used to enhance textbooks by adding information specific to specific classes.

Furthermore, voids in worksheets offer opportunities for pupils to fill in gaps and build knowledge. When used with appropriate

teaching approaches, well-designed worksheet questions can pique students' interest. Worksheets also serve a variety of purposes in various circumstances. Teachers can use worksheets as an assessment tool to comprehend students' prior knowledge, learning outcomes, and learning processes, and students can also use them to track their own learning progress.

The Learner Activity Sheet (LAS) is one type of material that can be employed (worksheet). Teachers and students will benefit from the worksheet. Media is a message-channeling tool that can excite students' thoughts, feelings, and talents to make the teaching and learning process more effective and efficient. The teacher can assess the learner's knowledge by using this material. Not only would it be used as an assessment but also as a source of communication between the teacher and the learner.

During the A Phase, the teacher guides the students through a process in which they demonstrate ideas, interpretations, mindsets, or values and create information that will form part of their knowledge in reflecting, relating, or applying it effectively in any situation or context. This also necessitates teachers encouraging students to create conceptual structures, allowing them to integrate new and old knowledge. The validation of student activity sheets was found to be good in a study titled *The Development of Students' Activities Sheet with a Scientific Approach in Elementary School* (Simbolon et al., 2018). It also demonstrates that student activity sheets are used as learning materials in English classes at a high rate, with around 80% of students using them. The results of a pre-test and post-test conducted by researchers in two different classes show improved learning achievement in both students. As a result, it was determined that the students' activity sheets developed by researchers using a scientific approach are worthy of being used as teaching material to support the fourth grade of primary school.

Certainly, learning activity sheets/worksheets encourage kids to engage on their own and look for a solution on their own. They develop logic in the children. They can teach children how to think. Their logic builds up as they try to find solutions and answers themselves. Hence, the goal of LAS is to allow students to take an active role in their learning by assisting them in developing and discovering concepts through different process skills and serving as a resource for teachers and learners during the learning process.

Considering the above perspectives, the researcher was encouraged to conduct this study on the analysis and evaluation of the contents of learning activity sheets (las) developed as key instruments to the recovery of learning loss and gaps in the new normal to determine if the learning activity sheets are aligned with the competencies expected to be taught to the learners; to determine if the learning activity sheets are suited or appropriate into the level of the learners; and to determine if the learning activity sheets are comprehensive enough for the learners to acquire the necessary skills.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the learning activity sheets (LAS) in English which served as inputs for an action plan during the school year 2023-2024. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the degree of evaluation of the English Experts and the Teachers as regards the contents of the learning activity sheets (LAS) in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. appropriateness;
 - 1.2. accuracy;
 - 1.3. usefulness;
 - 1.4. clarity; and
 - 1.5. comprehensibility?
2. Is there a significant difference between the evaluation of the two groups of respondents regarding the degree of evaluation of the contents of the learning activity sheets (LAS) with respect to the above-cited aspects?
3. What action plan may be proposed to improve the contents of the developed learning activity sheets (LAS)?

Methodology

Research Design

The method of research that was used in the study was descriptive. The method of research used in the study was the descriptive type. Ary (2018) states that research design is the researcher's plan for understanding some group or phenomenon in its context. Scientific research describes events, phenomena, or facts systematically dealing with a certain area or population. The survey research design plays a pivotal role in the study, attempting to establish the range and distribution of some social characteristics, such as education or training, occupation, and location. It also aims to discover how these characteristics may be related to certain behavior patterns or attitudes, thereby significantly impacting the study's outcomes. The data were collected from at least a part of the population as the basis for assessing the incidence, distribution, and interrelations of phenomena and variables as they occur in people's lives.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This was conducted in the selected schools in the Fourth District of Quezon. The respondents of the study were composed of English Experts and teachers. Each instrument was administered to all the respondents. The respondents were given enough time to answer the research instrument.

Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators for every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part was the evaluation of the respondents. The second part was the comments and suggestions of the English expert and teacher-respondents.

The questionnaires that served as the survey instrument of the study were subjected to a comprehensive validation process, ensuring their correctness and validity. The contents of the questionnaire were meticulously analyzed and scrutinized by Field Experts, whose comments and feedback were carefully considered in the final approval of the method. The consultant, acting as the proofreader of the researcher, examined the questionnaire again, further reinforcing the thoroughness of the validation process and the quality of the research.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the conduct of the study. Upon approval of the school's division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the English expert and teacher-respondents of the selected public secondary schools in the Fourth District, Division of Quezon, and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency and Percentage Distribution – Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

t-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference between the degree of evaluation of the two groups of respondents as regards the contents of learning activity sheets (LAS).

Ethical Considerations

This study shall protect the privacy of the respondent and shall not in any means expose confidential information.

Results and Discussion

This part dealt with the gathered data that were analyzed and interpreted for the better understanding of the study. The framework of the analysis and interpretation was guided by the problems stated in the objectives of the study.

Table 1. Respondents' Evaluations As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Appropriateness

<i>The contents of the Learning Activity Sheets are suited:</i>	<i>English Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. to the level of the learners.	3.83	SA	4.07	SA
2. enough to meet the objectives of the lessons.	3.63	SA	3.40	A
3. for individual and group activity.	3.80	SA	3.50	SA
4. for the pupils to perform all the tasks given.	3.70	SA	3.60	SA
5. enough to enhance the HOTS or critical thinking ability of the pupils.	3.67	SA	3.73	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.73	SA	3.66	SA

Legend: WM, Weighted Mean; VI, Verbal Interpretation; VA, Very Agree; A, Agree

As shown on Table 1 with respect to the first criterion which is Appropriateness, the overall weighted mean obtained for the English Experts is 3.73, while the teachers is 3.66 which is verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. All of the respondents answered Strongly Agree except for some respondents belonging to the list of the teachers who answered Agree on the second indicator - suited enough to meet the objectives of the lessons. This means that the contents of the learning activity sheets which were used are appropriate to meet the objectives of the lessons.

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Accuracy

<i>The contents of the Learning Activity Sheets are crafted properly to help:</i>	<i>English Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. the teachers and pupils generate ideas properly.	3.90	SA	3.83	SA
2. the teachers and the pupils compile information.	3.67	SA	3.67	SA
3. the teachers and the pupils analyze ideas presented.	3.73	SA	3.77	SA
4. the teachers and the pupils make or draw reflections.	3.57	SA	3.63	SA
5. the pupils create output efficiently.	3.73	SA	3.77	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.72	SA	3.73	SA

As revealed on Table 2 with respect to the second criterion which is Accuracy, the overall weighted mean obtained for the English Experts is 3.72, while the teachers is 3.73 which is verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

The respondents have parallel evaluations in all the indicators of the second criterion. This implies that both the English experts and the teachers have recognized the accuracy of the contents of the learning activity sheets and that they are benefited in the discussion of their lessons.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Usefulness

<i>The contents of the Learning Activity Sheets are utilized to:</i>	<i>English Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. allow pupils to make connections among pieces of information and make information easier to recall.	3.73	SA	3.87	SA
2. allow pupils to break information into manageable chunks, so that they can easily see the relationships among separate ideas.	3.50	SA	3.80	SA
3. provide a means for teachers to observe and assess the pupils' thought processes.	3.57	SA	3.73	SA
4. provide opportunity to every pupil fill out information properly.	3.67	SA	3.87	SA
5. help and provide opportunity to every pupil learn and think independently.	3.57	SA	3.90	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.61	SA	3.83	SA

As displayed on Table 3 with respect to the criterion, which is Usefulness, the overall weighted mean obtained by the English experts is 3.61, while the teachers is 3.83 which is verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

All of the respondents have parallel evaluations in the five indicators of the third criterion.

This generally shows that the contents of the learning activity sheets are useful enough as the indicators are being justified by the respondents. This further implies that both the English experts and the teachers found the contents of the learning activity sheets very beneficial and useful as tools to facilitate better learning.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Clarity

<i>The contents of the Learning Activity Sheets are clear enough to:</i>	<i>English Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. provide valuable opportunity for critical thinking among pupils.	3.63	SA	3.70	SA
2. explain sequence and show relationship among related ideas.	3.63	SA	3.63	SA
3. provide better understanding among pupils.	3.53	SA	3.50	SA
4. be used by the pupils which allow them to play an active role in learning.	3.47	A	3.73	SA
5. for pupils to make abstract comparison, evaluations and conclusions.	3.53	SA	3.73	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	SA	3.66	SA

As reflected on Table 4 with respect to the criterion, which is Clarity, the overall weighted mean obtained by the English experts is 3.56, while the teachers is 3.66 which is verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

The two groups of respondents have evaluated the five indicators with a similar perception.

This revealed that using the learning activity sheets would help the teachers explain lessons and the learners to learn which, furthermore, provide them with clearer concepts.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Comprehensibility

<i>The contents of the Learning Activity Sheets will:</i>	<i>English Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. benefit all learners in understanding the concept of part to whole.	3.67	SA	3.83	SA
2. benefit all learners to record relationships, clarify and organize ideas.	3.63	SA	3.77	SA
3. benefit all teachers to show and explain relationship between and among content.	3.57	SA	3.70	SA
4. motivate pupils and help visual learners acquire information more easily.	3.50	SA	3.63	SA
5. help pupils comprehend texts and be assisted in pre-writing techniques.	3.47	A	3.70	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.57	SA	3.73	SA

As seen on Table 5 with respect to the criterion, which is Comprehensibility, the overall weighted mean obtained by the English experts is 3.57, while the teachers obtained 3.73 which is verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

The indicators of the fifth criterion spelled the benefits of the learners in understanding the concept of part to whole, in recording relationships, clarifying and organizing ideas; in showing and explaining relationship between and among content; in motivating and helping visual learners acquire information more easily; and in helping pupils comprehend texts.

The results show that the contents of the learning activity sheets are comprehensive enough to help the pupils acquire and answer information easily.

In addition, the results imply that using this LAS would help a lot for the learners to perform tasks easily.

Table 6. Summary of Respondents' Evaluations on the Learning Activity Sheets

Criteria	English Teachers		Subject Area Chairmen	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
Appropriateness	3.73	SA	3.66	SA
Accuracy	3.72	SA	3.73	SA
Usefulness	3.61	SA	3.83	SA
Clarity	3.56	SA	3.66	SA
Comprehensibility	3.57	SA	3.73	SA
General Weighted Mean	3.64	SA	3.72	SA

Legend: OWM – Overall Weighted Mean

As revealed on Table 6 with respect to the five criteria which are Appropriateness, Accuracy, Usefulness, Clarity, and Comprehensibility, the general overall weighted mean obtained by the English experts is 3.64, while the teachers is 3.72 which both are verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. It can be seen that in all the criteria on evaluating the contents of the learning activity sheets, the English experts and the teachers have expressed their evaluations using the scale Strongly Agree.

This generally implies that the evaluations of the two groups of respondents do not differ. This further implies that the developed learning activity sheets were found appropriate, accurate, useful, comprehensive and clear to be used in the discussion of the lessons and in facilitating better learning of the learners.

Table 7. Test of Difference between the Evaluations of Respondents on As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Appropriateness Using z Test

Respondents	WM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z Values ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
English Experts	3.73	0.87	0.31	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.66	0.81				

Legend: s – Standard Deviation α – Level of Significance Ho – Null Hypothesis

As displayed on Table 7, the critical z values are -1.96 and 1.96, and the computed z value is 0.31. Since the computed z value is between the ranges of critical z values, -1.96 to 1.96, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is not enough evidence at 5% level of significance to support that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of English experts and teachers on the contents of the learning activity sheets as regards appropriateness.

This means that both the English experts and the teachers have the same evaluation as regards the appropriateness of the learning material developed.

Table 8. Test of Difference between the Evaluations of Respondents on As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Accuracy Using z Test

Respondents	WM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z Values ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
English Experts	3.72	0.87	-0.06	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.73	0.78				

Legend: s – Standard Deviation α – Level of Significance Ho – Null Hypothesis

The computed z value of -0.06 as seen on Table 8 is within the range of critical z values, -1.96 to 1.96, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is not sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of English experts and teachers on the material developed as regards accuracy.

This further implies that the views of the two groups of respondents believed that the developed learning activity sheets were accurate enough to be used to help the learners acquire information easily.

Table 9. Test of Difference between the Evaluations of Respondents on As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Usefulness Using z Test

Respondents	WM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z Values ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
English Experts	3.61	0.99	-0.97	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.83	0.81				

Legend: s – Standard Deviation α – Level of Significance Ho – Null Hypothesis

As shown on Table 9, the computed z value of -0.97 is inside the range of the critical z values, -1.96 to 1.96, at the 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there is not sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of English experts and teachers on the LAS developed as regards usefulness.

This implies that both the English experts and the teachers have similar evaluations regarding the usability of the developed learning

material. This further explains that both of the respondents found the use of this beneficial on their part as well as to their students.

Table 10. *Test of Difference between the Evaluations of Respondents on As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Clarity Using z Test*

Respondents	WM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z Values ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
English Experts	3.56	1.02	-0.43	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.66	0.78				

Legend: s – Standard Deviation α – Level of Significance Ho – Null Hypothesis

As presented in Table 10, the computed z value of -0.43 is between the critical z values of -1.96 and 1.96, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It shows that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of English experts and teachers on the developed learning activity sheets as regards clarity.

The result implies that the evaluations of both the English experts and the teachers on the five indicators of clarity are the same. This further explains that the developed LAS provide a clearer understanding of the context of the lesson.

Table 11. *Test of Difference between the Evaluations of Respondents on As Regards the Contents of the Learning Activity Sheets in Terms of Comprehensibility Using z Test*

Respondents	WM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z Values ($\alpha=5\%$)	Decision	Interpretation
English Experts	3.57	0.99	-0.69	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Teachers	3.73	0.79				

Legend: s – Standard Deviation α – Level of Significance Ho – Null Hypothesis

In Table 11, it shows that the computed z value of -0.69 is between the ranges of critical z values, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is not sufficient evidence at 5% level of significance to show that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of English experts and teachers on the developed LAS as regards comprehensibility.

This means that the two groups of respondents have parallel views regarding the comprehensive use of the developed LAS. This further elucidates that these are understandable enough for the students to perform tasks efficiently.

Table 12. *Summary of Test of Difference between the Evaluations of Respondents on the Learning Activity Sheets Using z Test*

Criteria	Computed z Value	Critical z Values	Decision	Interpretation
Appropriateness	0.31	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Accuracy	-0.06	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Usefulness	-0.97	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Clarity	-0.43	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant
Comprehensibility	-0.69	± 1.96	Fail to Reject the Ho	Not Significant

Based on Table 12, the computed z values of appropriateness, accuracy, usefulness, clarity, and comprehensibility are within the range of critical z values of -1.96 and 1.96, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. It means that the evaluations of English experts and teachers on the developed LAS do not differ significantly.

These findings imply that both the English experts and the teachers have similar views regarding the evaluations of the developed LAS. These also mean that the respondents are strongly aware in using these materials in their lessons considering appropriateness, accuracy, usefulness, clarity, and comprehensibility.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study the following conclusions are made:

Learning Activity Sheets could be developed by the English experts and the teachers themselves to be used in teaching English.

The developed Learning Activity Sheets are very acceptable to the English experts and teachers in terms of appropriateness, accuracy, usefulness, clarity, and comprehensibility.

The following recommendations are hereby offered:

The Learning Activity Sheets may be utilized as teaching tools to determine the performance of the students in English who would not only learn the topics but would also encourage active engagement or participation while learning.

Similar studies may be conducted by other researchers in other subject areas as well.

Further studies may be done focusing on the development of learning materials are also suggested to be conducted which would test the effectiveness of the teaching and learning outcomes to improve the performance of students.

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